

PEDAGOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE THINKING OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Annotation: This thesis discusses the pedagogical foundations of the development of creative thinking of elementary school students in the educational process. Discussions of researchers-scientists on the development of creative thinking are also presented.

Key words: pedagogical activity, creativity, primary education, observation, comparison, individual, reproductive level.

Introduction.

It is necessary to scientifically analyze the concept of "pedagogical conditions" in order to determine the pedagogical conditions that help to develop the creative thinking of elementary school students during the educational process. According to the explanatory dictionary of D. N. Ushakov, conditions are defined as mandatory conditions, necessary conditions that determine the existence and implementation of something.¹

V. L. Muravyov gives a pedagogical direction to the definition of "conditions" and defines them as requirements and recommendations for the organization of pedagogical activities subject to the general principles of the pedagogical process.

Pedagogical conditions, According to the definition of Yu. K. Babansky, "the environment in which the components of the educational process are presented in the best interaction and allows the teacher to work effectively, manage the educational process, and students to work successfully."

Today, the living conditions of a person are changing, at the same time there are changes in the educational process, the parameters of the world around us are changing rapidly. All these changes have led to the fact that actions on characteristics within the framework of standard knowledge, skills and competences do not allow to adapt to changes in modern society.

In the modern world, many demands are placed on human activity, one of which is his creativity. Development of a creative personality in the process of education and upbringing becomes one of the socially important tasks of

¹ Толковый словарь русского языка. Том I. Под ред. Д.Н. Ушакова. – М.:ООО «Издательство Астрель», ООО «Издательство АСТ», 2000. – 848 с.

modern education. The school itself must produce a successful, well-rounded person who can go beyond the standard set of knowledge, skills and abilities, make their own choices and make decisions. Only such a person can live decently in the new world.

Primary school age is the most favorable period to start forming the qualities of a creative person, to develop his creative thinking.

Creativity is the basis of the ability to create, to find new, to make decisions and to act outside the original and established form. Researchers identify the following levels of development of creative thinking: theoretical, reproductive-creative, creative-reproductive. A person at the theoretical level of developing creative thinking is distinguished by the desire to acquire knowledge about the essence of the theory of creativity. The development of creative skills at the reproductive and creative levels is carried out at the individual reproductive level.

The process of purposeful and systematic development of creative thinking is characterized by the creative-reproductive level of the development of creative thinking, holistic and systematic development is the level of authorship.

The transition from one level of development of creative thinking to another is carried out on the basis of a person's readiness to develop a higher level of development of creative thinking (psychological, scientific, pedagogical and practical).

Primary school age is an important stage in a child's development, which is convenient for identifying and developing a child's creative thinking, because at this age their various aspects develop:

- basics of creative and educational trajectory;
- psychological base of effective activity;
- based on the creative attitude to the world around us, a set of values, qualities, abilities, and needs of a person is formed.

Creative thinking of elementary school students, which is carried out in educational activities, becomes an effective force only when the internal intentions of students correspond to the objective tasks set by the teacher.

Therefore, the development of creativity inherent in each student, the development of the qualities necessary for this, first of all, means the creation of pedagogical conditions that contribute to this process.

At primary school age, it is necessary for the teacher to manage the process of developing creative thinking on the basis of pedagogical skills, which are:

- should be a carrier of developed creative thinking;

- organizes an educational process characterized by a creative, developmental and humanistic direction;
- organizes this process scientifically, methodically and technologically;
- based on the age characteristics of students, creates pedagogical conditions.

Successful development of creative thinking of a primary school student occurs only when certain conditions are created that help its formation. The following conditions are emphasized in the psychological and pedagogical literature.

The first condition is to change the role of the student. To fundamentally change the role of primary school students in the educational process, according to which he should take the position of an active participant in knowledge, who has the opportunity to choose, satisfy his needs and interests, and realize his creative thinking. Personal and active interaction of students and the teacher is necessary in performing creative tasks. Its essence is to understand the continuity of direct and reverse influence, interaction as co-creation.

In addition, creating a comfortable psychological environment is an important condition. Creating this environment that helps to develop creative thinking: encouraging children's desire for creativity, believing in the strengths and capabilities of primary school students, unconditional acceptance of each student, his wishes, needs, thoughts, interests respect, refrain from comments and commands. Negative emotions (fear, anxiety, self-doubt, etc.) have a negative effect on the result of creative activity, especially in elementary school students, because they are characterized by excessive emotionality. It is necessary to create a friendly atmosphere, care for everyone, confidence and a moderate demand environment among elementary school students, which can be controlled.

The next pedagogical condition is the creation of internal motivation for learning. The importance of the internal motivation of education should be understood by his attitude to the work of the elementary school student, his high self-esteem, self-confidence. Only based on them, it will be possible to develop the creative thinking of elementary school students. Then the cognitive need, the desire of the child, his interest not only in knowledge, but also in the search process itself, spiritual upliftment will serve as a reliable guarantee that more mental stress will lead to extra work and benefit the child.

Proper pedagogical support for a child can be divided into the following conditions. Intelligent, unobtrusive, benevolent help, this is help, not the advice

of a teacher. There is no need to do anything for the student if he can do it himself. If the reader can think about something, you can't think about it.

It should be noted that a condition for the development of creative thinking is a combination of different forms of work. Depending on the goals of creative task performance by elementary school students and its level of difficulty, the best combination of frontal, group, and individual work forms of students in the educational process. The advantage of individual and group forms is that collective research allows combining the accumulated knowledge, skills and abilities of several students, helps to increase the intensity of reflection, which plays an important role in the process of creating innovation. In the process of thinking, a young student knows not only creative activity, but also himself in the process of creativity (his desires, motives, needs, opportunities, etc.), which allows him to change the direction of education.

Intersubjectivity is also one of the conditions for the development of creative thinking. When solving creative problems, as a rule, knowledge from relevant and different fields should be used, and the more difficult the task, the more knowledge and effort should be spent to solve it.

Creating a success condition is distinguished as the following condition. Tasks of a creative nature should be done together by students of the whole class. Only success in their implementation is evaluated. The teacher should see individuality in each student. You should not personally prepare creative for the most successful students and not replace with them the simple tasks given to all students of the class.

It is also important for every student to do creative work independently. Independently solving problems that require the greatest effort for a student, if the child reaches the limit of his capabilities and gradually increases it. For elementary school students, complex but possible tasks are needed that activate interest in creative activity and develop appropriate skills for this activity.

The variety of creative tasks is one of the conditions for the development of creative thinking of elementary school students, both in terms of their content and forms of presentation, as well as in terms of complexity. Optimal combination and exchange of creative and conventional educational tasks have rich development opportunities, each primary class allows to organize the work of the teacher in the zone of proximal development of the student.

Consistency is an important condition in the development of creative thinking of primary school students, the episodic nature of creative tasks and exercises provided in any program of primary education does not help to

activate the creative activity of students, and thus primary school does not have enough influence on the development of students' creative thinking.

Modern life requires flexibility of thinking and creativity in solving the problems that arise in the individual. How much society will advance in the near future will be determined by the creative thinking and, therefore, cognitive activity of the modern young generation. The use of educational technologies creates an environment of creative research, increases the knowledge and activity of primary school students².

Pedagogical conditions that contribute to the development of creative thinking of elementary school students through problem-based educational technologies in the educational process include: development of flexibility, speed, accuracy and originality of thinking of elementary school students selection of special tasks using enabling technologies.

Selection and systematization of tasks of programs designed for creative development of elementary school students during the educational process, data processing using problem-based learning technologies, problem-based education for the development of creative abilities of elementary school students is an important stage in the use of technologies. At the stage of developing the lesson, it is necessary to determine the purpose of the lesson in accordance with the state educational standard of primary general education, to select the educational programs from the point of view of teaching, development, and educational functions.

Providing a comfortable creative environment in the lesson that contributes to the free expression of creative thinking. To demonstrate creative thinking, you need a unique environment - an atmosphere of comfort, goodwill, freedom, in which a student of primary school age will have the opportunity to create. Therefore, in order to develop the creative thinking of elementary school students, joint activities of the team with interactive interaction are organized, the teacher directs the students' activities and directs their behavior.

² Гилфорд. Д. Три стороны интеллекта // Психология мышления / Ред. А. М. Матюшкин. — М.: Прогресс, 1965.-525 с.-С. 447.

The use of problematic educational technologies in education provides the teacher with not only highly qualified specialized knowledge, but also knowledge in the field of educational technologies, as well as existing methods and forms of organizing the educational process using technology. Qualified specialists who combine extensive experience with professional knowledge and skills are needed to work with problematic educational technologies.

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